

Japanese Figures in the Video Game Industry: Yūzō Koshiro

Andrés Domenech Alcaide

CoolJapan.es

Good morning, readers. On this occasion, we will take a slight turn, and instead of focusing on a video game director or producer, I will focus on the long and distinguished career of Japanese composer Yūzō Koshiro, one of the most famous and influential music and sound designers in the history of video games. He is particularly well known for his iconic works of the 1980s and 1990s and is closely associated with companies such as Sega and Nintendo.

Early Years: A Young Talent Shaped by His Family

Yūzō was born in Tokyo in 1967, and a love for music ran in his family, as his mother, Tomo, was a professional pianist. In fact, the piano would be the first instrument the young Yūzō learned to play, starting at the age of three. By the age of five, he was already playing it fluently, and years later, he received musical training from the renowned composer Joe Hisaishi, whom you may remember for his work on, among many other films, those produced by Studio Ghibli and Hayao Miyazaki.

Both his mother, Tomo—a musical performer—and his sister, Ayano—an illustrator and designer—would have a notable influence on Yūzō's future projects, as we will see later.

However, with the rise of electronic music and the novelty of working with synthesizers and computers, Koshiro became captivated by the passion he began to feel for digital composition, without abandoning his interest in traditional instruments. During his secondary education, he started experimenting with compositions of all kinds on his NEC PC-8801 computer.

With this computer, he even created playful tributes or humorous nods to the soundtracks of famous video games from companies like Sega, Namco, or Konami. This allowed him to understand the tempos and composition methods required for video games, knowledge he would later apply in his professional work.

The games that inspired him to pursue a career in the industry were true classics, such as *Gradius* and *Space Harrier*, both released in 1985.

Entering the Video Game Industry

Yūzō Koshiro in his youth, alongside several computers, including his NEC PC-8801 (on the left)

In 1986, just after reaching adulthood, he joined Nihon Falcom, a company considered a pioneer in Japanese role-playing games—and which would influence companies like Square and Enix in creating titles such as *Final Fantasy* and *Dragon Quest*.

Unfortunately, at the time, Nihon Falcom and its games were less known outside Japan during the 1980s, due to the massive boom of consoles like Nintendo's NES—since Falcom focused primarily on the Japanese market and games for personal computers.

In 1985, Koshiro sent a demo cassette with some of his works to the company, which was well received. Part of his compositions were incorporated into the video game *Dragon Slayer II: Xanadu*, specifically for its expansion called “*Scenario II*.” *Xanadu* was a role-playing game in the dungeon crawler style, which would become popular years later with games like *Etrian Odyssey* or *Shin Megami Tensei*. It was released on various personal computers, including the NEC PC-8800 series and MSX computers. This franchise would go on to influence later series such as *Final Fantasy*, *Dragon Quest*, and *The Legend of Zelda*. Following this, Yūzō Koshiro officially joined Nihon Falcom's team.

He also worked on the game *Romancia*—the third instalment of the *Dragon Slayer* series—as well as *Dragon Slayer IV* and *Sorcerian*. However, the games that brought the most recognition to both Yūzō Koshiro and Nihon Falcom were the *Ys* series, in which Koshiro participated from the very first two instalments (1987 and 1988).

Cover art of *Dragon Slayer II: Xanadu – Scenario II* (1986) and *Ys I: Ancient Ys Vanished* (1987)

Yūzō Koshiro’s work during this period—and in the years that followed—was closely tied to his ever-reliable PC-8801 and its sound chip. He would continue using this computer for composition even years later, despite having access to far more advanced equipment.

After his early years, Koshiro began working as a freelance composer, in order to avoid being tied to a single video game company or studio—much like composers such as Nobuo Uematsu would later do. His work from this time can be heard in games such as *Bosconian*—a Namco space shooter in which players could move through the level with near-total freedom. He also worked for the company Quest, responsible for titles such as *The Scheme* and the *Ogre Battle* series.

He also composed the music for the visual novel *Misty Blue* by Enix in 1990. It was during this period that his international recognition began to grow, as both Sega and Nintendo took notice of his work throughout the decade.

His timeless works for Sega and Nintendo

It was at Sega where he would create the most famous soundtracks of his career—those most beloved by fans. However, he also produced notable work for games developed for Nintendo consoles.

Koshiro was ahead of his time. While video games already featured strong musical compositions, he went further—developing his own music programming languages (or adapting existing ones) to create pieces that worked both within the context of the game and as standalone music. In fact, Yūzō Koshiro still performs concerts featuring these soundtracks, and both original versions and reinterpretations by electronic music enthusiasts can be heard in clubs around the world today.

It was through his work with Sega and Nintendo during the 16-bit era that he became one of the most recognized composers in the industry, thanks to three key titles: *The Revenge of Shinobi* (1989, Sega Mega Drive/Genesis), *ActRaiser* (1990, Super NES), and *Streets of Rage—Bare Knuckle* (1991, Sega Mega Drive). Each of these games featured completely different influences, showcasing the wide range of musical genres that shaped Koshiro's compositions. *Revenge of Shinobi* delivers a blend of techno, beat, and disco music, combined with Asian and ethnic influences.

ActRaiser, on the other hand, features a distinctly European, classical, and partially epic style. For this game, Koshiro developed a system for the Super NES that allowed for a greater number of instruments to be reproduced, overcoming the limitations of the console's audio channels. Since multiple tracks had to share limited channels and instruments, Koshiro's method dynamically loaded musical sections as needed by each track. This system would later be adopted by other games in which he was not directly involved, such as those in the Mana series and the Tales of franchise.

Original cover art of *The Revenge of Shinobi* and *ActRaiser*

Streets of Rage, for its part, offers one of the most memorable soundtracks in video game history—one that also functioned perfectly as dance music. Drawing from techno, progressive, funk, breakbeat, and house influences, it left players astonished by the sheer variety of sounds produced by what would now be considered the limited sound chips of consoles at the time.

Koshiro was one of the pioneering video game composers in creating highly catchy soundtracks that players could easily remember after only a few minutes of listening. Moreover, several of his compositions pay homage to well-known musical styles and tracks, as can be heard in pieces such as “Go Straight” and “Fighting in the Street” from *Streets of Rage 2*, which draw clear inspiration from house, techno, and late-1980s club music, as well as contemporary artists and production techniques of that era. This intertextual approach allowed his music to resonate not only within the context of the game, but also within the broader landscape of electronic music culture.

It is also important to understand the significant role that the founding of the company Ancient in 1990—and Koshiro’s involvement in it—played in his career. Ancient worked closely with companies such as Sega, Nintendo, and Sony on the development of games in which Koshiro participated. The company was founded by Yūzō Koshiro together with his mother, Tomo Koshiro. His sister, Ayano, contributed designs to the Streets of Rage games, as well as to the ActRaiser and Ys series.

Koshiro also composed the soundtrack for the Master System version of *Sonic the Hedgehog*—a version entirely different from the game released for the Sega Mega Drive/Genesis in 1991, although it retained some influences and elements from the Mega Drive soundtrack composed by Masato Nakamura. In doing so, he applied his experience from 16-bit development to an 8-bit sound environment.

The soundtracks of his games were commercially released—something quite uncommon at the time. In fact, the soundtrack of *Streets of Rage 2* (*Bare Knuckle 2*, 1992) became one of the albums to reach top sales charts in Japan. It was during this period that he began collaborating with composer and producer Motohiro Kawashima.

For *Streets of Rage 3* (1994)—originally titled *Bare Knuckle 3* in Japan—he once again worked alongside Kawashima and attempted to create a revolutionary sound for video games at the time. This included the use of randomized and algorithmic sound sequences to generate beat and techno rhythms, allowing for the incorporation of effects that would have been difficult to conceive through conventional composition methods.

Yūzō Koshiro also composed the soundtrack for the Sega CD version of *Eye of the Beholder*—a role-playing game based on *Dungeons & Dragons*. He was also among the first video game composers to take a serious interest in digital music production and the use of the Compact Disc as a medium for video game soundtracks.

Cover art of *Streets of Rage 3* and *Eye of the Beholder*

Yūzō Koshiro Today

The Tokyo-born composer has never stopped working, although his golden years were undoubtedly the 1990s, when the entire video game industry was astonished by the novelty of his sound—especially considering that the Mega Drive, the console most closely associated with his work, was often regarded as having “inferior” audio capabilities compared to its direct competitor, the Super NES.

His position as a freelance composer has allowed him to avoid being tied to any single company—although many still tend to associate Yūzō Koshiro primarily with Sega—and he has worked with all major video game companies, including Nintendo, Sega, Sony, and Microsoft. From the mid-1990s into the early 2000s, his prominence declined somewhat, despite continuing to work on various titles that did not achieve the same impact as Sega’s classic beat ’em ups.

This situation changed when a former Sega veteran approached Koshiro to take part in a new project that would become one of the most important video games in history: *Shenmue* (1999, Sega Dreamcast). In this work, we see a more classical side of Koshiro, rather than his more modern, DJ-oriented style.

Yū Suzuki, creator of many of Sega’s most important franchises, brought him on board—alongside composers such as Takenobu Mitsuyoshi and Takeshi Yanagawa—for the two *Shenmue* titles released on Dreamcast.

This opportunity helped restore part of Koshiro’s former recognition, and since then, various video game companies have continued to collaborate with him, often in the role of a guest composer—similar to inviting a well-known figure to contribute to a project—given his importance within the industry, much like composers such as Nobuo Uematsu or Motoi Sakuraba.

He worked on original titles such as *Car Battle Joe*, a game inspired by the *Wangan Midnight* manga and developed by Ancient. He has also contributed to crossover titles—games that bring together characters and elements from different franchises—such as *Namco x Capcom* and Nintendo’s Super Smash Bros. series, where he even arranged themes originally composed by Kōji Kondō, such as the main theme of *The Legend of Zelda*, as well as works by Junichi Masuda.

In a similar vein, he has also been involved in crossover projects such as *Project X Zone 2* (2015) and *Puzzle & Dragons X* (2016). He also contributed to the Castlevania series in 2006, working alongside Michiru Yamane—herself a composer worthy of dedicated study—, whose work, along with that of other composers commonly associated with Konami and Namco, has influenced Koshiro’s own style.

Among his most notable recent works are his contributions to the soundtrack of *Kid Icarus: Uprising* (2012, Nintendo 3DS), alongside Motoi Sakuraba and other composers, and, most significantly, his role as the main composer for the Etrian Odyssey series. Developed by Atlus and originally released on Nintendo DS, Koshiro worked on the series from its first instalment in 2007 through its latest numbered entry in 2016 for Nintendo 3DS.

Original cover art of *Shenmue* (1999) and *Etrian Odyssey* (2007)

One of the latest collaborations we are aware of from Yūzō Koshiro in the industry is his work on the video game *Monster Boy and the Cursed Kingdom*, released in 2017 for PC, PlayStation 4, Xbox One, and Nintendo Switch.

In this project, he once again worked alongside Michiru Yamane and Motoi Sakuraba, as well as Keiki Kobayashi, Takeshi Yanagawa, and Haruka Shimotsuki. The game is part of Sega's Wonder Boy/Monster World series.

Koshiro is well aware of the impact that video game music has had on the broader music industry—having influenced electronic music composers beyond the realm of gaming. DJs, bands, and composers from around the world, such as Nick Dwyer, Flying Lotus, Dizzee Rascal, Kode9, and Ikonika, have acknowledged the influence that Koshiro's work—and that of other Japanese composers—has had on their own music.

Yūzō has performed concerts around the world and has taken part in numerous video game events. He has also appeared in club settings as a DJ, as can be seen in various recordings. His music has reached global audiences, including performances in symphonic concerts held in iconic venues such as the Gewandhaus in Leipzig, and he has even been honoured by the Japan BGM Philharmonic Orchestra.

Enthusiasts and professional bands around the world have created arrangements and reinterpretations of his music. There have also been remastering projects of classic games he worked on, such as the well-known *Streets of Rage Remake*, developed by a largely Spanish team—an unofficial project that was ultimately shut down by Sega—in which several composers paid tribute to the original soundtrack by Koshiro and Kawashima for the *Streets of Rage* franchise.

Promotional artwork for *Monster Boy and the Cursed Kingdom*, 2017

Although Yūzō Koshiro's most renowned work was concentrated in the 1980s and 1990s, his career has remained remarkable in the last decade, both through direct musical projects and his ongoing influence on the global video game music culture, as can be observed throughout the previous paragraphs.

After his involvement in *Monster Boy and the Cursed Kingdom* in 2017, Koshiro continued collaborating with studios and franchises seeking his unique compositional style. Between 2018 and 2023, he worked on soundtracks for several independent and collaborative projects, notably contributing remixes, arrangements, and adaptations for titles updating classic retro-era games. His creative approach allowed iconic video game pieces to receive contemporary reinterpretations without losing their original identity, thus bridging generations of fans and new audiences.

In 2019 and 2020, Koshiro also participated as a guest composer in various anime and multimedia productions related to video games, applying his expertise in electronic music and digital orchestration to expand his artistic reach beyond consoles. Simultaneously, his presence in international soundtrack concerts and specialized music festivals intensified significantly, with regular performances across Europe, Asia, and the Americas celebrating both his classic repertoire and more recent creations.

One of Koshiro's most notable contributions in the last decade was his work on the *Etrian Odyssey Origins Collection* soundtrack, a remastered compilation that brought together themes from the *Etrian Odyssey* series with new instrumentation and modern arrangements. This collection was enthusiastically received by veteran fans and also introduced Koshiro's original music to thousands of new listeners, reinforcing his legacy as one of the most influential composers in Japanese video game history.

After more than a decade of anticipation, and seeing fans produce tribute projects or unofficial remakes of early titles, *Streets of Rage* returned with an official release in 2020: *Streets of Rage 4*, developed by Dotemu and endorsed by Sega.

In addition to the new music composed by Olivier Derivière, the title included contributions from several veteran Japanese musicians, including Koshiro himself.

The composers joining the project included Harumi Fujita —veteran of Capcom and SNK, as well as a freelance composer—, Yōko Shimomura —one of the most renowned composers in the industry, known for work on franchises such as Street Fighter and Kingdom Hearts—, Keiji Yamagishi —composer of classic games like the original *Ninja Gaiden* (1988)—, and of course, Motohiro Kawashima, Koshiro’s frequent collaborator and co-creator of the Streets of Rage style.

With the main theme, character selection theme, and first-level track, “They’re Back,” composed by Koshiro for this release, the music successfully conveyed that 26 years had not passed between the titles. The soundtrack felt higher quality due to modern technology but retained a classic feel, as Koshiro focused on creating timeless pieces with memorable melodies.

Beyond his work as a composer, Yūzō Koshiro has continued to influence generations of musicians and producers working with digital and electronic sound, collaborating on educational and music research projects exploring the intersection of generative music, algorithms, and traditional composition. In this sense, his figure remains a reference point in both academic and professional fields, frequently cited in studies on video game music history and its international cultural impact on video game and electronic music.

Sources

- **Texts consulted:** Game Atelier, Red Bull Music Academy, Sega, The Verge, Harcdcoregaming 101 | **Text created by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es]
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